

Financial Value Added (FVA) in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research

Eka Wahyu Hestya Budianto, Nindi Dwi Tetria Dewi
Universitas Islam Negeri Maulana Malik Ibrahim Malang
wahyu.ala@uin-malang.ac.id

Abstract: This study aims to determine the research mapping regarding the Financial Value Added (FVA) ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking using a mix-method approach, namely the VOSviewer bibliometric study and Library Research. Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications around the FVA ratio; (2) mapping the results of the VOSviewer bibliometric visualization around the FVA ratio based on the number of clusters and their items; and (3) mapping research topics around the FVA ratio using a Library Research study. The results showed that: (1) based on the distribution of journal publications, there were 25 journal publications regarding the FVA ratio; (2) based on the mapping of the VOSviewer bibliometric study, the network visualization results around the FVA ratio are divided into 4 clusters and 82 topic items; (3) based on the mapping of Library Research studies, there are 2 topics around the influence of the FVA ratio and 2 topics about the determinants of the FVA ratio. The implications and contributions of this research are to map research topics around FVA ratios in Islamic and Conventional Banking which are often or rarely researched by researchers so that they can be a reference for subsequent researchers.

Keywords: Financial Value Added (FVA), Bibliometrics, VOSviewer, Library Research, Islamic and Conventional Banking

Introduction

Financial Value Added (FVA) is a financial ratio used to measure the creation of added value by a company. In the banking context, FVA is used to measure how much added value a bank creates for its shareholders, taking into account the capital costs incurred to finance its business activities. FVA is calculated by subtracting the weighted average cost of capital (WACC) from the bank's total profit. WACC capital costs are costs incurred by banks to obtain the capital needed to carry out their business activities, and include their own capital costs and debt costs. The higher the WACC, the greater the costs the bank must incur to finance its business activities.

In calculating FVA, bank profits are calculated after deducting operational costs, interest costs and taxes. Then, the WACC capital cost is multiplied by the bank's total capital, and the result is subtracted from the total net profit that was calculated earlier. If the FVA is positive, then the bank has created sufficient added value for its shareholders, whereas if the FVA is negative, then the bank should reconsider its business strategy. One of the advantages of using FVA is that it provides a more complete picture of the added value generated by the bank compared to other financial ratios such as ROE (Return on Equity) or ROA (Return on Assets). ROE and ROA only take into account the net profit generated by the bank without taking into account the capital costs incurred, so they do not provide a complete picture of the bank's performance in creating added value. Even though the use of FVA is still not as popular as some other financial ratios such as ROE or ROA, FVA is increasingly being used by several large banks in the world as a measure of their financial performance. This is especially true because FVA can provide a more

complete picture of the added value generated by banks, and can help banks evaluate their long-term performance.

Research regarding the use of FVA in banking continues to develop along with the increasing interest of researchers in digging deeper into this financial ratio. Several studies have been conducted to test the effectiveness and relevance of using FVA as a measuring tool for banking financial performance. First, several studies show that FVA is a better measure for measuring banking financial performance compared to other financial ratios such as ROE or ROA. This is because FVA considers the capital costs incurred by the bank, so it can provide a more accurate picture of the added value created by the bank for its shareholders. Second, several studies also show that FVA can help bank management make the right investment decisions and maximize the added value generated by the bank. For example, FVA can be used to evaluate whether a proposed investment will produce added value greater than the capital costs incurred. Third, there is also research that shows that FVA has several limitations and cannot always provide an accurate picture of a bank's financial performance. Some of the limitations of FVA include the difficulty of determining the correct cost of capital, as well as the sensitivity of FVA to market fluctuations and interest rates. Overall, the development of research on FVA in banking continues to develop and shows the potential of FVA as an effective and relevant financial performance measurement tool. However, it is important to remember that FVA cannot be the only financial performance measure used by banks, and should be used in conjunction with other financial ratios to provide a more complete picture of a bank's financial performance.

The aim of this research is to map research topics around FVA in Banking using: (1) the VOSviewer bibliometric method to analyze and study maps of literature development in publications in a scientific field by creating a metadata network map; and (2) literature study review to analyze, identify and review articles from national journals indexed by Google Scholar and accredited by Sinta. The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains all research topics surrounding FVA. This can be a reference for other researchers who wish to research FVA. The implication and contribution of this research is to map research topics surrounding the FVA ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking which are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that they can become a reference for subsequent researchers.

Literature Review

Financial Value Added (FVA) is a method of measuring company performance that considers the cost of capital or Cost of Capital in generating added financial value. The FVA concept aims to measure how effectively a company uses available capital to generate profits above the capital costs incurred. FVA is calculated by subtracting the cost of capital from the net operating profit generated by the company. The cost of capital can be calculated as the sacrifice required by capital owners to provide capital for the company. The cost of capital can come from loan sources (debt) and shares (equity) and is usually calculated using the Weighted Average Cost of Capital (WACC). In practice, companies can use FVA as a more accurate and transparent performance measurement tool, especially in measuring management performance regarding the use of company funds. As a performance measurement tool, FVA can help management to identify areas where the company can improve efficiency and generate greater added value for shareholders.

Bibliometric studies are research methods used to quantitatively analyze literature or information sources in a particular field. This method involves collecting data from bibliographic databases, such as Scopus or Web of Science, to evaluate the characteristics of publications and study patterns and trends in them. Bibliometric studies can be used to identify and study the most widely discussed research topics

in a field, map collaboration networks between researchers and institutions, and estimate the impact or influence of research using indicators such as the number of citations or journal impact factor. This method can also provide information about the development of publications in a field over a certain period of time, as well as compare scientific production between countries, institutions or certain researchers. In practice, bibliometric studies are often used in scientific research and as an aid in decision making in various fields, such as the development of public policy, evaluation of the performance of institutions or researchers, as well as in market or industrial research. VOSviewer is free software used to analyze bibliometric data and visualize relationships between keywords, articles, authors, or topics in literature. This software was developed by researchers at the Eindhoven University of Technology in the Netherlands and has been used widely in bibliometric research. VOSviewer uses network analysis and clustering techniques to map relationships between keywords, articles, or authors in bibliometric data. This software can retrieve data from a variety of sources, including bibliographic databases such as Scopus or Web of Science. Once data is entered, VOSviewer can be used to perform bibliometric analysis, such as identifying the most discussed research topics in the literature, analyzing collaborations between researchers, or mapping citation networks between publications. VOSviewer can also be used to create visualizations of bibliometric analysis results. These visualizations can take the form of network graphs, co-citation graphs, or cluster maps, allowing users to more easily understand the relationships between keywords, articles, or authors in the literature. In practice, VOSviewer is often used by researchers to gain deeper insight into research trends within a field, as well as to identify collaborations and research gaps that may need to be filled in the future.

Studies Library Research is a research method carried out by systematically and comprehensively collecting, reviewing and analyzing relevant literature or sources of information in a particular field or topic. This method aims to gain a better understanding of the topic being researched or to identify weaknesses and strengths in previous research. Library Research studies involve searching for sources of information such as journal articles, books, reports, and other documents that are relevant to the topic being researched. Once the sources of information are collected, researchers will read and review each source of information carefully, note important information, and organize their findings into appropriate categories. In a Library Research study, researchers will also analyze and evaluate sources of information that have been collected using certain criteria, such as the quality of research methodology, credibility of sources, validity of findings, and contribution of research to the topic being researched. Library Research studies are very useful for providing a comprehensive and systematic review of research that has been conducted in a particular field or topic. This study can help researchers understand developments in research that has been conducted, identify gaps in research, and identify new research questions or ideas that can be explored further. Apart from that, literature studies reviews can also be used to provide a basis for developing or testing new theories in research.

Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in Library Research studies. The research object is Financial Value Added (FVA). The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is research journal articles on FVA in Sharia and Conventional Banking.

The source of data collection comes from search for accredited national journals, Sinta via the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba) and Perish/Harzing software. Data analysis tools use Microsoft Excel software, Mendeley Desktop, and

VOSviewer. Data collection techniques include: (1) opening Perish/Harzing software, then search for journals based on the title words category with the keywords " Financial Value Added " and " FVA" throughout the year; (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications regarding FVA using Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop based on publication year; (2) map the results of bibliometric network visualization and journal publication trends around FVA using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) mapping research topics around FVA using a Library Research study.

Results and Discussion

Mapping the Distribution of Scientific Publications regarding Financial Value Added (FVA) in Sharia and Conventional Banking

There are 25 national journals accredited by Sinta based on the results of data collection using Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop originating from the Garuda website (Garba Reference Digital) and Perish/Harzing software during the period 2010 to 2023. The results are as follows:

Table 1. Journal publication data about FVA by year

Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications
2010	1	2016	1	2020	3
2011	1	2017	1	2021	4
2012	1	2018	2	2022	7
2015	1	2019	2	2023	1

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 201 6.

VOSviewer Bibliometric Study Mapping on Financial Value Added (FVA) in Sharia and Conventional Banking

Search results for articles on software Perish/Harzing are exported in RIS (Research Information Systems) format, then input and analyzed using VOSviewer software. The results are as follows:

Figure 1. Network visualization of a map of research developments around FVA.

Source: Processed data, software VOSViewer 1.6.18.

Software visualization results VOSViewer related to the research development map regarding the FVA ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking, there are 4 clusters and 82 topic items in the mapping, including the following:

- Cluster 1, consists of 30 topic items, namely: added value, assets, average value, Indonesian stock exchange, capital, concept, cost, data, difference, equivalent depreciation, financial performance method, financial ratio/value added, fva, investor, performance, qualitative, measurement, merger, performance measurement method, net profit, nopat, performance measurement, performance measurement, ratio, ratio, return, roa, stock price.
- Cluster 2, consists of 22 topic items, namely: analysis, calculation, certain period, company, depreciation, descriptive research, eva measurement, financial performance/ratio analysis/report/statement, form, literature study, management, net income, eva value, performance, positive results, profit, quantitative approach, secondary data, shareholder.
- Cluster 3, consists of 19 topic items, namely: coal subsector mining company, doid, efficient financial performance, fva analysis technique, fva value, idx, indonesia stock exchange, itmg, kkgi, market value added, mva result, negative fva value/mva value, operating profit, positive eva value, ptba, purposive sampling technique, smmt.
- Cluster 4, consists of 11 topic items, namely: work analysis, economic value added, eva method, mva method, company, company, purposive sampling, research method, sampling technique.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around the Influence of Financial Value Added (FVA) in Sharia and Conventional Banking

Library Research study in previous research journals, researchers found 2 effects of ratios Financial Value Added (FVA) in Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely:

First, share prices. The influence of FVA on share prices in banking can be explained as follows:

- (1) Shows more accurate company financial performance. In a banking context, FVA can be used to measure how effective a bank is in generating profits that exceed the capital costs incurred. This is important because banking is a business that is very dependent on capital and the trust of customers. FVA can provide more accurate information about a company's financial performance compared to traditional financial performance measurement methods, such as Return on Investment (ROI) or Earning per Share (EPS). This is because FVA takes into account the capital costs incurred by the company, whereas traditional financial performance measurement methods do not take into account capital costs. By using FVA, companies can evaluate their financial performance more accurately and make better investment decisions. Apart from that, FVA can also help companies determine more effective business strategies to create value for their shareholders.
- (2) Attract investors. Investors tend to be interested in companies that have stable and increasing financial performance over time. Therefore, banks can show an increase in their FVA from year to year to attract investor interest. Banks can show their strategies to increase FVA. These strategies may include improving operational efficiency, reducing costs, or increasing revenue. Investors will feel more confident if companies have a clear plan to improve their financial performance. Banks can show a comparison of their FVA with their closest

competitors to show how they are performing relative to each other. If a bank's FVA is higher than competitors, this can be a strong selling point to attract investors. Investors tend to look for companies that have financial reports that are transparent and easy to understand. Therefore, banks can ensure that their financial reports are easy to understand and show how FVA is calculated.

- (3) Increase company value. To increase company value through FVA, banks can take several steps. Banking can increase ROI by increasing revenue or reducing costs. Some ways that can be done are by offering more profitable products and services, expanding market reach, carrying out product innovation, increasing operational efficiency, or carrying out operational restructuring. Banking can reduce the cost of capital by reducing the level of risk and improving asset quality. Some ways that can be done are by strengthening risk management, improving credit quality, expanding funding sources, or establishing strategic partnerships with other parties. Banks can optimize capital structure by choosing the right combination of own capital and loans. In this way, banks can balance loan costs and profits obtained through the use of their own capital. In the long term, by increasing FVA, banks will be able to increase company value significantly. This can happen because FVA helps banks to identify investments that generate added value and reduce unprofitable investments. That way, banks can focus more on investments that have the potential to provide greater profits and increase company value in a sustainable manner.

Second, financial performance. In the banking industry, FVA can have a significant impact on financial performance. In the long term, increasing FVA can help banks to improve their financial performance. FVA can also help banks to identify the most effective policies and strategies in creating added value for shareholders. Some of the ways in which FVA can influence banking financial performance include:

- (1) Increase the efficiency of capital allocation. In the banking context, FVA can be used to measure the efficiency of capital allocation in banks. By measuring the added financial value generated by a bank, FVA can help bank management make better decisions about capital allocation. In this case, FVA can help banks to evaluate their business performance and prioritize their capital allocation to the most profitable business areas. FVA can also help banks evaluate the risk and return of their investments. By using FVA to measure the financial added value of an investment, banks can compare the added value generated with the capital costs incurred for the investment. This can help banks in selecting investments that provide higher added financial value and minimize the risk of unprofitable investments. Thus, the use of FVA can help banks increase the efficiency of their capital allocation and improve their overall financial performance.
- (2) Drive increased profitability. In a banking context, FVA can be used to encourage increased profitability. FVA is calculated by subtracting the capital costs incurred by the company from the net profit generated. The cost of capital can be calculated as the weighted average of a company's cost of equity and cost of debt. If the FVA value is positive, then the company has created added value for shareholders. In banking, FVA can be used to measure financial performance and to motivate management to increase profitability. Banks can use FVA to identify the most profitable products and services, as well as to prioritize the use of their capital. By focusing investment on products and services that generate positive FVA, banks can increase their profitability. FVA can also be used as a management performance measurement tool and as a basis for providing incentives to managers. Managers can be given incentives based on their contribution to the creation of added financial value

for the company. This can encourage managers to make better business decisions and be more oriented towards added value.

- (3) Increase company growth. In the banking context, FVA can be used to increase company growth by optimizing the use of capital and increasing operational efficiency. By using FVA, banks can find out whether the investment they make produces added value that is greater than the capital costs incurred. FVA can also help banks make strategic decisions such as allocating resources and determining the right business focus. By knowing the added value generated by each business line or product, banks can determine priorities for developing businesses that produce greater added value. Apart from that, FVA can also be used as a tool to increase banking transparency and accountability. By measuring the added value generated, banks can provide clearer and more open information to investors and stakeholders regarding company performance.

Mapping the Library Research Study regarding the Determinant Variables of Financial Value Added (FVA) in Sharia and Conventional Banking

Library Research study in previous research journals, researchers found 2 determinant variables of the Financial Value Added (FVA) ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely:

First, acquisition. Acquisitions can have a significant impact on FVA in banking, especially if the acquisition is carried out wisely and effectively. Here are some ways in which acquisitions can affect FVA:

- (1) Increase the scale of operations. In the era of digitalization, technology is the key to increasing the efficiency and scale of banking operations. Banks can develop technology platforms that can be used to automate processes, reduce operating time, and increase data management efficiency. Apart from that, technology can also help banks to expand their reach and access to new markets. Banks can expand branch networks to reach a wider market share. In this case, banks must consider strategic locations and ensure that these branches can provide high-quality services. Mergers and acquisitions can help banks to expand the scale of operations and strengthen market positions. When carrying out mergers and acquisitions, banks must consider the right strategy, carry out careful analysis, and ensure that the merger can produce added value for the company. Employees are an important asset in banking. Therefore, banks must ensure that employees have the skills and competencies required to scale operations. Apart from that, banks must also provide training and career development for employees so they can keep up with technological developments and market competition. Although increasing the scale of operations is the main goal, banks must also pay attention to the quality of the services provided. Good service quality will help banks to maintain and increase customer trust, so that they can expand market share and increase profits.
- (2) Portfolio diversification. In banking, portfolio diversification can be done in various ways. Sector diversification: Banks may choose to allocate their assets to different sectors of the economy, such as manufacturing, agriculture, energy, or financial services. This way, if one sector experiences stress, investments in other sectors can still provide stable returns. Geographic diversification: Banks can allocate their assets to different geographic regions, such as Asia, Europe, or North America. This way, if economic conditions in one region decline, investment portfolios in other regions can still provide stable returns. Diversification of investment types: Banks can allocate their assets to various types of investments, such as stocks, bonds, money markets, or commodities. This way, if one type of investment declines in value, the other type of investment can still provide stable returns. Time diversification: Banks

can choose to allocate their assets to short-term and long-term investments. This way, if long-term investments decline in value, short-term investments can still provide stable returns. Risk diversification: Banks may choose to allocate their assets to investments that have varying risks. This way, if one investment experiences a loss, other investments that have lower risk can still provide stable returns. When diversifying their portfolio, banks need to consider factors such as investment objectives, risk profile and current market conditions. Proper portfolio diversification can help banks reduce risk and improve their investment performance.

- (3) Increase efficiency. There are several ways that can be done to increase efficiency in banking. Business process automation: Banking can adopt technology such as business process automation to reduce the time and costs incurred in carrying out daily operations. Automation can be applied to various aspects such as banking operations, risk management, and asset management. Increased operational efficiency: Banking can optimize the use of resources and reduce operational costs through cutting unnecessary operational costs and using appropriate information technology. Branch network optimization: Banking can optimize its branch network by evaluating the performance of each branch and closing branches that are inefficient or unprofitable. Meanwhile, branches that have good performance can have their services improved and used as a base to reach new customers. Improving service quality: Banks can improve their service quality in various ways such as increasing customer service efficiency, optimizing customer complaint systems, and providing training and development to staff who interact directly with customers. Digitalization and Innovation: Banking can introduce new product and service innovations and increase the use of digital technology such as mobile banking and internet banking. Digitalization can help banks reduce costs, increase efficiency and improve customer experience. By implementing this strategy, banks can increase operational efficiency, reduce costs, and improve the quality of their services to meet customer expectations.
- (4) Increase market share. To increase market share in banking, there are several things that can be done. Offer competitive products and services: Banks must offer products and services that are better or superior to their competitors. This could be higher interest on savings or deposits, lower fees on loans, or digital banking services that are easier to use. Improve customer experience: Customers should feel comfortable and happy when interacting with the bank. Banks can improve the customer experience by providing friendly and efficient customer service, as well as ensuring that their products and services are easy to use and easy to access. Reaching a wider market: Banks should expand their reach by targeting a wider market. This can be done by opening new branches in unreached areas or expanding the ATM network. Innovate: Banks must continue to develop new products and services that suit customer needs. This could be developing more sophisticated digital banking applications, or offering more innovative investment products. Improve branding and marketing: Banks should improve their branding and marketing to attract the attention of potential customers. This can be done with more aggressive advertising campaigns or sponsorship of events related to their target market. In implementing the strategies above, banks must pay attention to and fulfill customer needs and desires in order to increase their market share.

However, acquisitions can also have a negative effect on FVA if not carried out properly. For example, if an acquisition is made at an excessively high price or if there is excess capacity in the acquired operations, this can reduce the bank's FVA. Therefore, it is important for banks to carry out careful analysis and ensure that acquisitions are carried out wisely and effectively.

Second, merger. The impact of the merger on FVA can be seen from several factors, namely:

- (1) Increasing Business Scale. In some cases, mergers can result in an increase in the scale of a banking company's business. This can increase the company's operational efficiency and effectiveness as well as strengthen its market position and competitiveness. In the long term, increasing efficiency can increase company profits and reduce capital costs, thereby having a positive impact on FVA.
- (2) Integration Risks. However, the negative impact of a merger is the integration risk that may occur. Unsuccessful integration can result in additional costs and disrupt well-running operations. Additional costs that arise can be from consolidation costs, restructuring costs, employee dismissal costs, or even legal costs. Integration failure can reduce the company's operational efficiency and effectiveness, thereby reducing the company's FVA.
- (3) Changes in Ownership and Management Structure. Changes in ownership and management structure may affect FVA. In general, a successful merger will result in more effective and efficient management, which can increase the company's FVA. However, if the merger results in a significant change in ownership structure, this can affect the company's performance and reduce FVA.
- (4) Purpose of Merger. The purpose of the merger may also affect FVA. For example, if a merger is carried out to strengthen market position, this can increase the company's competitiveness and have a positive impact on FVA. However, if the merger is carried out to avoid losses or reduce operational costs, this can reduce FVA.

In conclusion, the impact of mergers on FVA in banking companies depends on several factors. If the merger is carried out well, this can increase the company's FVA by strengthening market position and increasing operational efficiency. However, if it fails, a merger can negatively impact a company's FVA by increasing additional costs and reducing the company's operational efficiency and effectiveness.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows: first, the number is based on mapping research publications around the ratio Financial Value Added (FVA) in Sharia and Conventional Banking during the period 2010 to 2023 which comes from the accredited national journal Sinta, there are 25 published journal articles. Second, based on the VOSviewer bibliometric study mapping, the network visualization results regarding the FVA ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking are divided into 4 clusters and 82 topic items. Cluster 1 consists of 30 topics, cluster 2 consists of 22 topics, cluster 3 consists of 19 topics, and cluster 4 consists of 11 topics. Third, based on Mapping Research Topics using Library Research, there are 2 topics related to the influence of the FVA ratio in banking, namely: stock prices and financial performance. And there are 2 topics related to the determinants of the FVA ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely: acquisitions and mergers.

References

- Baranuri, M. Y., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Akad Ijarah pada Industri Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038971>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2022). *Pemetaan Penelitian Akad Mudharabah Pada Lembaga*

Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik Vosviewer Dan Library Research. *J-EBIS (Jurnal Ekonomi Dan Bisnis Islam)*, 7(1), 43–68. <https://doi.org/10.32505/j-ebis.v7i1.3895>

- Budianto, E. W. H. (2022). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Akad Musyarakah pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. *JESI (Jurnal Ekonomi Syariah Indonesia)*, 12(1), 25–36. [https://doi.org/10.21927/jesi.2022.12\(1\).25-36](https://doi.org/10.21927/jesi.2022.12(1).25-36)
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Bibliometric And Library Research Of Financing Risk In Islamic Banking. *JPS (Jurnal Perbankan Syariah)*, 4(1), 79–97. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.46367/jps.v4i1.1031>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RISIKO REPUTASI PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LIBRARY RESEARCH. *Al-Masraf: Jurnal Lembaga Keuangan Dan Perbankan*, 8(1), 94–113. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.15548/al-masraf.v8i1.425>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Risiko Kredit pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. *BANCO: Jurnal Manajemen Dan Perbankan Syariah*, 5(1), 20–34. <https://doi.org/10.35905/banco.v5i1.4987>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). RESEARCH MAPPING ON CREDIT RISK IN ISLAMIC AND CONVENTIONAL BANKING. *AL-INFAQ: Jurnal Ekonomi Islam*, 14(1), 73–86. <https://doi.org/10.32507/ajei.v14i1.1862>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2022). Research Mapping of Musyarakah Contracts in Islamic Financial Institutions: VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research. *Maliki Islamic Economics Journal*, 2(2), 76–94. <https://doi.org/10.18860/miec.v2i2.17199>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Akad Ju'alah pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10040276>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Akad Sharf pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10042641>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Biaya Operasional terhadap Pendapatan Operasional (BOPO) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. *JAF (Journal of Accounting and Finance)*, 7(1), 34–48. <https://doi.org/10.25124/jaf.v7i1.5995>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan penelitian rasio Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037417>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Dividend Payout Ratio (DPR) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037141>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Dividend Per Share (DPS) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. *Al-Mal: Jurnal Akuntansi Dan Keuangan Islam*, 4(1), 109–126. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.24042/al-mal.v4i01.16760>

- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan penelitian rasio Economic Value Added (EVA) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037270>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Financial Value Added (FVA) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. *BJRM (Bongaya Journal of Research in Management)*, 6(2), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.37888/bjrm.v6i2>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Net Operating Margin (NOM) pada Perbankan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. *Ecobankers: Journal of Economy and Banking*, 4(2), 84–94. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8323115>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan penelitian rasio Net Profit Margin (NPM) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037209>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RASIO NON PERFORMING FINANCING (NPF) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LIBRARY RESEARCH. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038983>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RASIO RETURN ON INVESTMENT (ROI) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LIBRARY RESEARCH. *Kompetensi (Competence: Journal of Management Studies)*, 17(1), 66–82. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.21107/kompetensi.v17i1.20002>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RASIO WORKING CAPITAL TURNOVER (WCT) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LIBRARY RESEARCH. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037081>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar cash ratio pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037415>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037413>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar current ratio pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037359>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar pengaruh variabel mikroekonomi: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037254>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar quick ratio pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038973>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pengaruh Book Value per Share (BVS) pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. *Islamic Economics and Business Review*, 2(1). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185250>
- Budianto, E. W. H., Dewi, N. D. T., & Abidin, U. A. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio

- Dana Pihak Ketiga (DPK) Pada Perbankan Syariah Dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik Vosviewer Dan Library Research. *Syiar Iqtishadi: Journal of Islamic Economics, Finance and Banking*, 7(1), 25–44. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.35448/jiec.v7i1.19887>
- Budianto, E. W. H., Saputra, H. M. G. A., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Koperasi Jasa Keuangan Syariah (KJKS): Studi Bibliometrik VOS viewer dan Library Research. *EL MUDHORIB: Jurnal Kajian Ekonomi Dan Perbankan Syariah*, 3(2), 131–148. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185180>
- Dewi, N. D. T., Ibad, N. N., Pratopo, G., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Manajemen Zakat Pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer Dan Library Research. *Jurnal Ekonomika Dan Bisnis Islam*, 6(1), 1–20. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.26740/jekobi.v6n1.p1-20>
- Febrian, J., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). THE EFFECT OF KNOWLEDGE, TRUST, PRODUCTS, SERVICES AND RELIGIOSITY ON INTEREST IN SAVING. *International Conference of Islamic Economics and Business 9th*, 85–96. <http://repository.uin-malang.ac.id/15487/>
- Gozali, M., Saputra, M. A., Dewi, N. D. T., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN SEPUTAR VARIABEL DETERMINAN RETURN ON EQUITY (ROE) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LIBRARY RESEARCH. *IDEI: Jurnal Ekonomi & Bisnis*, 4(1), 34–47. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.38076/idejeb.v4i1.151>
- Mawardi, M. I., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Tabungan Pensiunan Nasional (BTPN) Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10049566>
- Putri, S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Bukopin Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10049572>
- Qudratullah, M. Q., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Akad Murabahah pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038979>
- Rahmawati, L., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar Bank Tabungan Negara (BTN) syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037422>
- Ratnasari, A. D., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Akad Rahn (Gadai) pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038977>
- Rofiah, A., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Akad Wadiah pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10042647>
- Rofika, H., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN SEPUTAR MAYBANK SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LIBRARY RESEARCH. *Jurnal Ekonomi: Journal of Economic*, 14(1), 28–39. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.47007/jeko.v14i01.6463>
- Rohimah, W., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian

seputar Bank CIMB Niaga Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. *Jurnal Ekonomi Manajemen Perbankan*, Vol 5, No 1 (2023): JEMPER Januari-Juni, 30–40. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185264>

Rohmandika, M. S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian seputar Variabel Determinan Return On Asset pada Perbankan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. *Eco-Iqtishodi: Jurnal Ilmiah Ekonomi Dan Keuangan Syariah*, 5(1), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.32670/ecoiqtishodi.v5i1.3607>

Shalsabila, I. H., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar akad kafalah pada industri keuangan syariah: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037426>

Sufia, I., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Akad Salam pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10042345>

Zahro, T. S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar akad istishna' pada industri keuangan syariah: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037428>